
Impact of Social Networking Sites on Undergraduate Students

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ABSTRACT

The social Networking sites are among the most popular destinations on the web. Undoubtedly, in certain instances, this has played a role in the development of Internet Addiction Disorder and fraudulent operations on the internet, and on the other hand have benefitted too, but have they generally improved the overall quality of life? Some contend that the advantages offered by social networking sites like Face book and Whatsapp etc have improved both society and the individual, and that as these sites continue to gain traction among a wider range of users, Finding a link between college students, use of social networking sites and their academic achievement has become a significant research project due to the increasing adoption of these sites by students.. Some people believe that since social networking sites became popular in the 1990s, students' academic performance has been neglected ,It is noted students; spend more time on social networking sites than they do on their coursework. The research seeks to achieve the following goals: Determining the use of social networking sites by the undergraduate students of different Medical/Engineering and Govt. Degree Colleges of Kashmir, To Determine the frequency of use of social networking sites, visiting the social networking sites and the effect of social media on reading habits. The study additionally aimed to explore the affects of social networking sites on their academics & their recommendations to their friends for use of social networking

sites based on their personal experiences. To achieve the above objectives the data was collected from 80 undergraduate students of different colleges of Kashmir valley.

Introduction:-

Social networks are online spaces and mobile applications that let people and groups interact, exchange information, connect, and build relationships. Individuals can establish connections with neighbors, family, friends, and those who share their interests. One of the most significant uses of the internet in modern times is social networking. People can maintain social ties, keep informed, access, and share a variety of information using popular social networking sites like Face book, Yelp, Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok. Additionally, these websites let advertisers connect with their intended audiences. Since SixDegrees.com, the first social networking site, was introduced in 1997, social networking sites have advanced significantly. Newer social networking sites are being quickly adopted by people worldwide these days. As per DataReportal, a January 2022 Kepios investigation revealed that the global count of social network users exceeds 4.74 billion.

Following the launch of SixDegrees in 1997, Open Diary in 1998, Mixi in 1999, Makeoutclub in 2000,[38][39] Cyworld in 2001,[40][2], this newer generation of social networking sites started to take off. Friendster and Nexopia in 2003, Hub Culture in 2002. Cyworld emerged as a pioneering enterprise to reap financial benefits from the virtual commodities trade. In 2003, MySpace and LinkedIn were introduced, while Bebo followed in 2005. Although the majority of Orkut's early users were from the United States, the social networking site swiftly gained popularity in India and became the first widely used one in Brazil (Madhavan, 2007). Social networking services gained popularity very quickly; in 2005, MySpace had more page views than Google.

The social Networking sites gave rise to wide sharing of information and connectivity; Social networking sites provide chances for networking and teamwork. Individuals can participate in cooperative initiatives, join clubs and communities, and establish connections with experts in their industry, provided more Business Opportunities, Social networking sites has been instrumental in bringing social concerns to people's attention, supporting social causes, and inspiring people to take action and effect positive change.

The social networking sites have also gave rise to misinformation's, cyberbullying, addiction and time consumption. Social media sites are a treasure trove of information, an ocean of knowledge but we are

wasting our valuable time browsing unnecessary things. There are far too many benefits, and negative affects include improper use of these websites and increased time spent on social media, which can lead to addiction.

Many studies (Barnes & Laird, 2012; Carroll & Kirkpatrick, 2011; Gok, 2015; Nehls & Smith, 2014; O'Keefe & Pearson, 2011) were conducted to determine the positive and negative effects of social networking sites. Schill (2011) reported that social media is the negative impacts (anxiety, behavioral changes, mental health problems, psychological effect, severe loss of personal productivity, stress, a sense of guilt and crisis, etc.)

Literature Review:-

According to Englander et al. (2010), the usage of social media in academics has more disadvantages than advantages. Social media severely impacts the academic performance of a student. The addiction to social media is found more among the students of higher studies which ruins the academic excellence of an individual (Nalwa & Anand, 2003). Among the social media users, Facebook users' academic performance was worse than the nonusers or users of any other social media network. Facebook was found to be the major distraction among students (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). However, other studies report contrary findings and argued that students benefited from chatting (Jain et al., 2012), as it improves their vocabulary and writing skills (Yunus & Salehi, 2012). Social media can be used either to excel in academics or to devastate academics. It all depends on the way it is used by the students. The good or bad use of social media in academics is the users' decision because both the options are open to the students (Landry, 2014). Haneefa & Sumitha (2011) conducted a survey on perception and use of SNS by the students of Calicut University by collecting data through structured questionnaire from a selected sample of 150 students. The study establishes that majority of the students aware with SNSs and use for friendly communication where Orkut was mostly used SNSs. At the same time, lack of security and privacy are the main distresses of SNSs users. Hamade (2013). Kuppuswamy and Narayan (2010) studied the impact of social networking sites on the education of youth. The study finds that social networking websites have both positive as well as negative impact on the education of youth, depending on one's interest to use it in a positive manner for his or her education and vice versa. Pratyasha Jain (2011) this paper is focused to find out the answer whether the social networking sites are boon or bane for today's society. Social networking websites like Orkut, Facebook, MySpace and YouTube are becoming more and more popular and has become part of daily life for an increasing number of people. Because of their features, young people are attracted to social networking sites. Effect of social

networking sites usage on the studies of Nigerian students This study evaluates the effect of social networking sites on the students and justifies that no significant effect of these sites are found to hamper their studies but there is no clear balance of its usage. Students do not realize as to when and where to use these social networking sites and are witnessed using them in areas such as lecture halls while lectures are going on and also during study and reading hours of their work schedules. This incorporates the suggestion to youth in order to efficiently allocate their time and reschedule their timings to face terms with what needs to be done. From Lenhart & Madden (2007) point of view social networking websites provide a virtual life to those students who use social networking websites to make new friends although every contact and friend is virtual and un-real. Some of users register themselves in social networking websites because they want others to know about them, for such reason students get registered and make friends, students thought that increasing number of friends could make them famous among other friends but unfortunately social networking websites provide virtual contacts. Tinto (1997) reviews that new information on social networking websites encourages growth and provide students with an ever growing learning community which inreturns substitute both academic and social success. Cormode and Krishnamurthy (2008) says that in today world of Internet there are many social networking websites but among all of them the social networking websites which entertain user with special and detailed information profile are more liked by people instead of other social networking websites which provide fewer features. Wang, Q., Chen, W. and Liang, Y. (2011) in their study 'The Effects of Social Media on College Students' found that most of the college students used social media and spent many hours checking social media sites, there was a negative aspect to college students' use of social media.

Objectives

- To determine the percentage of users of social Networking sites.
- To know the frequency of usage of SNS by the users.
- To determine the frequency of visiting the social networking sites.
- To find out the impact on reading habits by using SNS.
- To find out the affects of SNS on Academics.

Methodology:-

In order to achieve the goals, a brief, organized questionnaire was sent via Google Form to UG Students of different Medical and degree colleges of Kashmir in order to collect the necessary data. In addition to this , content analysis was employed to compile earlier research on the subject.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION:-

Analysis has been conducted in accordance with the questionnaires questions. Tables, figures, and basic statistical computations have been employed in the data analysis process.

The gathered data analysis is presented under the following headings.

Table 1.0 Gender wise percentage of respondents

Total No. of Respondents	Male	Female
80	64	16

Table 1.0 shows the gender wise number of respondents. Among the total number of 80 respondents, 80% were male and 20% were female and Figure 1.1 shows the responses of UG students of different Medical colleges, Engineering and degree colleges of Kashmir, who are using and not using SNS, out of 80 respondents, 99 % were using SNS and 1% were not using SNS.

Figure 1.2:-Shows the percentage of UG Students using SNS Very often and occasionally

The Figure 1.2 reveals that the percentage of undergraduate students using SNS Very often and occasionally varies. Nearly 60 % of the students are using SNS very often and 40% are using SNS occasionally.

Figure 1.3:- The frequency of visiting SNS.

Figure 1.3 indicates that out of the 80 respondents, the majority of them are visiting SNS everyday and the percentage of students visiting every day is 79%, Once a week is 14%, once a month is 3% and twice a week is 4%.

Figure 1.5:-Impact of SNS on Reading Habits:-

Figure 1.5 reveals that out of the 80 respondents , 75% indicated that using SNS affects Reading Habits , while as 25% indicated that it does not affect the reading habits .

Figure 1.6 Affects of SNS on Academics:-

Figure 1.6 indicates that out of the 80 respondents, 65% said that there is negative affects on Academics, as there is mismanagement and wastage of time, while as 35% of respondents said that it has positive effect on academics as it is helpful to gain knowledge from SNS if the time is managed properly.

Figure 1.7:- % suggesting use of SNS to others:-

Figure 1.7 shows the analyzed results that only:-

1. 10% of total respondents suggest use of SNS to others.
2. 65% of respondents suggest below 50%.
3. 20% of respondents suggest between 50%-90%.

Findings and Conclusion:-

Given the latest survey available, in India there are about 470.1 million active social media users in 2022, Today's world is a global village. Everyone is connected to one another in this vast network generated by the Internet. Through SNS students can write their class assignment, they can check their results; they can also participate in different groups and social activities. On the contrary, too much use of SNS may hamper the academic performance of the students. So it is clear that Social Networking Sites have some positive and negative impacts. The following are drawn the findings and the conclusion:-

1. The sample was selected from the undergraduate students of various Medical students, Engineering and Arts students. Out of these 80 respondents 64 were male and 16 were female.
2. All of the respondents had social networking sites accounts. Respondents, having no social networking sites accounts were discarded because they were not eligible to answer our questions.
3. Further, respondents were asked to name the social networking sites they use. Majority of respondents were using multiple accounts.
4. Maximum of the respondents used SNS Very often.

5. Maximum of the respondents used SNS every day followed by once a week, then twice a week and then once in a month and the percentage varied from 79%, 14%,4%,3% respectively.
6. When the respondents were inquired that do the use of social networking sites effect the reading habits or not? Then maximum number of respondents answered that yes, the usage of these sites negatively affected the reading habits, 75% said it affects negatively and 25% said that it does not affect reading habits.
7. Majority of the respondents (75%) were of the view that the networking sites have negative affects on Academics and 35% were of the view that it has positive impact on academics.
8. Majority of the respondents were of the view that their academic performance decreased due to the increase in the use of social networking sites as it results in mismanagement and wastage of time.
9. In addition to above only little percentage of respondents (10%) suggested the use of SNS to others.

SUGGESTIONS:-

- According to the research, most students had three or more social networking sites. Therefore, I advise them to limit their usage to no more than two in order to spend less time on these sites and more effectively use it for their academic work. I suggest the students to limit their time spent on SNS and plan in such a way that they spend no more than an hour a day.
- I suggest to the students don't rely only on SNS.
- Since the majority of respondents said that social media was not making a significant contribution to their education, it can be concluded that social media is undoubtedly a study distraction that should be avoided when taking tests or engaging in other significant academic-related activities.
- Social networking sites can have both positive and negative effects on academics. Positively, they can facilitate collaboration, information sharing, and access to educational resources. However, they can also be a source of distraction, leading to decreased productivity and academic performance if not managed effectively. Additionally, excessive use of social media can contribute to procrastination and reduce time spent on studying or completing assignments. In many researches it is found that the more a student spends time in SNS the more his/her performance get worsened.
- Students underestimate the role of the teacher by using SNS.
- It is a double edged sword. It can have benefits also and if not used properly it can cut your progress into halves.

- Rather than relying solely on social media for communication, I proposed that students engage in more group-based activities to foster interpersonal skills and communication.
- Social scientists, psychologists, and other specialists should inform parents, students, and other stakeholders about the advantages and disadvantages of social media use;
- To ensure that the results are applicable to a wider audience, the study ought to be conducted with students of varying levels.

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